

PROBLEMS IN IDENTIFYING ENGLISH SINGLE CONSONANTS SILENT LETTERS: EXPERIENCE OF ENGLISH DEPARTMENT STUDENTS OF STATE ISLAMIC INSTITUTE OF KERINCI

Toni Indrayadi¹, Nuzmi Sasveri¹

¹State Islamic Institute of Kerinci, Kerinci-Jambi
toniyulia518@gmail.com, nuzmi0506@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to explore the experience of eighteen students of English department of state Islamic institute of kerinci in producing single consonants silent letters of plosive /t/ and /d/ and liquid /l/ in the middle of words, plosive /k/, and glide /w/ in the initial through surveys and semi-structured in-depth interviews. The research design was qualitative in the phenomenological approach (Conklin, 2007; Peters, 2010; Eddles-Hirsch, 2015). The interview were written verbatim in line format aligned according to the questions from the interview to help match or contradict corresponding responses from the different cases (Merriam, 2001), then analyzed and compare through comparative thematic analysis. In this study, we compare each participant theme to explain the data finding in pronouncing English single consonants silent letters. We identified three major factors that influence students' English pronunciation in interview, including (a) first language interference, (b) the knowledge of silent letters, and (c) the necessary of earliest pronunciation.

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.2582187

1. Introduction

All of the people on the world are hoped to pronounce English correctly like a native speaker of English. However, there are any problems make them unable to produce it in correct pronunciation, especially the Indonesian learners. This problem occurred because English has some inconsistency of sounds, the mother tongue interference and the influence of spelling on pronunciation [Hasan, 2014]. These factors are the main factors which influence the learners of English orally. Related to this study, the language interference is become the most influent factor which influence the students of Indonesian in identifying single consonant silent of English.

Mother tongue interference mean the interference of first language to target language as stated by Zhang [2009], the learner's first language is a significant factor which influence the pronunciation of the target language. For example Indonesian students pronounce the English silent letter *k* in "know" the same as the way to pronounce *k* in "kaki". In other words, they don't absent *k* in English word above. It occurred, because in Indonesia, the silent letters only occurred in vowel.

The mispronunciation of the silent letter above is the result of the over practice of the first language, a process of fossilization [Hasan, 2014]. This case is the root of poor pronunciation among the language

learners and users of a language [Chitulu & Njemanze, 2015]. The effect of this make the pronunciation of language learners hard to be understood by the native speakers of English in doing conversation. Therefore, it is need an effort to make the students understand English pronunciation variation in the process of teaching and learning in the class. From the brief explanation of Identifying single consonants silent letters above ,the researcher is triggered up and motivated to conduct a research on the Students' problem in identifying single consonant silent letters. It is to know the students problem in Identifying single consonants silent letters of English department students of IAIN Kerinci who have been studying pronunciation in teaching and learning process in the classroom.

2. Silents letters in English

Silent letters are the letters which is not pronounced in English vocabularies. Panse [2013] states that silent letter is the letter that spelled yet not pronounced. Moreover, Nordquist [2017] mentions that silent letter is an informal term for a letter alphabet that usually left unpronounced. It means, although the letters are exist in the words but they are not pronounced. Mathew [1998] who conducted the research on the mispronunciations of English consonants for Gayo and Acehnese that transfer, developmental factors, spelling interference, general processes and communicative strategies were the factors leading to the mispronunciations. Malay/Indonesian words are usually spelt the way they are pronounced. The alphabetical consonants and vowel are pronounce consistently as it alphabet Yong [cited in Swain, 2001]. Mother tongue of the English learners will influence the production of English as target language.

English pronunciation errors are sometimes specific to speakers of a certain language. The english learners who study English as second or foreign language find the problems in pronouncing certain English consonants and vowel Alimemaj [2014]. Based on the definition of the silent letters by scholar above, the single silent letters are occurred in the some letters. They are; *b, c,d,g, h,k,l,m,n,p,s,t,* and *w*. While in this study, the researchers only observe plosive /t/ and /d/ and liquid /l/ in the middle of words, plosive /k/, and glide /w/ in the initial. These five letters are usually found by the students in the process of teaching and learning English in the class. The example of five single silent letter can be seen in the below.

Table 1 The example of five single silent letter

Manner of Articulation	Letters	Words Examples			
		Initial	Transcript	Middle	Transcript
Plosive	t			Christmas Listen	/'kr ɪ sməs/ /lɪ sən/
	d			Handkerchief Wednesday	/hæ ŋkətʃɪf/ /'wenzdeɪ/
	k	Knife Knock	/naɪf/ /nɒk/		
Liquid	l			Calm Half	/kɑ:m/ /hɑ:f/
Glide	w	Wrap Write	/ræp/ /raɪt/		

Silent Letter in Indonesia

As mentioned by the scholar before that silent letters the letters which is spelled yet but not pronounced in a word. It means, although it is exist in words but it is not pronounced by the speaker. It is occurred, because the influence of the letter around them. There were also silent letters In Indonesia language, but it is only occurred in vowel, it is vowel *e*. There are two kind Vowel *e* sound in Indonesia [..... 2015], firstly is vowel *e* which is not pronounced in Indonesia, it is called *e* pepet (silent vowel) in Indonesia. And then *e* talling (pronounced vowel), it is vowel *e* which is pronounced in words. Both of the vowel will occurred differently in the words.

Tabel 2. Silent Letter in Indonesia

No	Letter	Word Examples			
		Silent e	transcript	Talling e	transcript
	e	Kental	/kental/	Preman	/préman/
		Jenis	/jenis/	lempar	/lémpar/
		Benar	/benar/	becak	/bécak/

3. Methods

A phenomenological approach was used in this study to get the data of the students' experience in producing silent letters in speaking class in the process of teaching and learning in the class at Islamic institute of Kerinci. Employing phenomenology approach is to examine the belief and behaviour of participants experience which is reflect on their career [Conklin, 2007; Peters, 2010]. The participants in this study were eighteen students English department students of Islamic institute of Kerinci who have taken speaking class. In selecting the participants in this study, purposive sampling was used characterized by specific criteria based on the research goals. To get dept answer from the participants, observation and in-depth interview were used. Then, in analyzing the data, we transcribed the data of students' interview, and then read them line by line. Having the analyzed the theme of each participant, we compared them in comparative thematic analysis. In this study, we compared each participant theme to explain the data finding in pronouncing English single consonants silent letters. To gain a valid data, we used member checking.

4. Findings

The experience of eighteen students of English department Islamic institute of Kerinci were presented and interpreted from their view points. As the previous study found that first language pronunciation interference influence the foreign language pronunciation. Researchers and linguists found in their research, the differences of the sound system between the (L1) and the (L2), the inconsistency of some sounds in English language, the mother tongue interference and the influence of spelling on pronunciation are the factors of mispronunciation of foreign or second language learnt [Hassan, 2014]. To overcome the pronunciation problems of English language learners, teachers must identify their pronunciation variations, which will provide teachers with ideas of designing differentiated teaching strategies for dealing with those students' problems in learning English pronunciation [Lin, 2014]. This study found that English department

students has been effort to pronounce English as correctly as possible, however the following factors challenge them, including (a) first language pronunciation interference, (b) the knowledge of silent letters, (c) the necessary of earliest pronunciation class.

The participants reported that during discussion in speaking class at the beginning of the semester, first language interference influence them when they produced English sounds. They produced English sounds as they produce their first language pronunciation, because in their first language all of consonants letter are pronounced wherever their position in the words. This makes students transfer their first language pronunciation to English pronunciation. Then, the participants reported the knowledge of silent letters and the necessary of earliest pronunciation class also influenced their English pronunciation. In the knowledge of silent letters, the students reported that guessed that all of the letters in English have the same pronunciation not depend on their position in the words. This problems make students did the same way in pronouncing the English silent letters. Furthermore, in the necessary of earliest pronunciation class, the students reported that it was needed to introduce an earliest pronunciation class at the beginning of semester when the students firstly attending the English department program.

5. Conclusion

From the finding of the study, the researchers can conclude that first language interference, the knowledge of silent letters and the necessary of earliest pronunciation need to be considered in the process of teaching and learning English as foreign language, because these factors is very essential for students in producing correct pronunciation. Thus, it is wise for the decision makers of the higher education, especially state Islamic institute of Kerinci to initiate the pronunciation class as soon as possible as the way to overcome the problems faced by students in pronunciation.

References

- [1] Alimenaj Z M 2014 English Phonological Problems Encountered by Albanian Learners *European Scientific Journal* **10** 8
- [2] Chitulu O M, Njemanze dan Queen U N 2015 Poor English Pronunciation among Nigerian ESL Students: The ICT Solution *Int. J. of Language and Literature* **3** 1 169-179
- [3] Conklin T A 2007 Method or Madness : Phenomenology as Knowledge creator *J. of Management Inquiry* **16** 3 275-287
- [4] Hasan E M I 2014 Pronunciation Problems: A Case Study of English Language Students at Sudan University of Science and Technology *English Language and Literature Studies* **4** 4
- [5] Lin L C 2014) Understanding Pronunciation Variations Facing ESL Students *Int. J. of Humanities and Social Science* **4** 5 16-20
- [6] Mathew I B 1998 Errors in Pronunciation of Consonants by Learners of English as A Foreign Language whose First Languages are Indonesian, Gayo, and Acehnese *Monash University Linguistics Papers* **3** 2 29-44
- [7] Nordquist R 2015 *Consonant (Sounds and Letters)* Glossary of Grammatical and Rhetorical Terms

- [8] Panse S 2013 *The Rules of Silent Letters* Retrieved from www.brighthubeducation.com
- [9] Peters M L 2010 A Phenomenological Study of the Experiences of Helping Professionals with Learning Disabilities *A Dissertation* (University of Massachusetts Amherst)
- [10] Yong J Y 2001 Malay/ Indonesian Speakers in Swain and B. Smith (Eds.) *Learner English's Guide to Interference and Other Problems* 279-295 (New York: Cambridge University Press)
- [11] Yong J Y 2015 *Perluakah Mengklasifikasikan Kembali E Pepet dan E Taling dalam Alfabet Indonesia?* Retrieved from <https://www.kaskus.co.id/thread/560b51bbc1cb1763448b4569>
- [12] Zhang F 2009 A Study of Pronunciation Problems of English Learners in China *J. of Asian Social Science* 5 6 141-146

